

Surface tension, Wettability and Tribological Properties of a Low Viscosity Oil Using CaCO₃ and CeF₃ Nanoparticles as Additives

José M. Liñeira del Río ^{a,b*}, A. Alba ^a, M. J. G. Guimarey ^a, Jose I. Prado^c, Alfredo Amigo ^d, Josefa Fernández ^a

^aLaboratory of Thermophysical and Tribological Properties, Nafomat Group, Department of Applied Physics, Faculty of Physics, and Institute of Materials (iMATUS), Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, 15782, Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

^bUnidade de Tribologia, Vibrações e Manutenção Industrial, INEGI, Universidade do Porto, Porto, Portugal.

^cCINBIO, Universidade de Vigo, Grupo GAME, Departamento de Física Aplicada, 36310 Vigo, Spain

^dLaboratory of Thermophysical and Surface Properties of Liquids, Department of Applied Physics, Faculty of Physics, University of Santiago de Compostela, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain.

*Corresponding author.

E-mail address: josemanuel.lineira@usc.es (José M. Liñeira del Río)

45 **ABSTRACT:** The rise of the electric vehicles as a more sustainable transport alternative makes it
46 necessary to study new transmission fluids that adapt to their needs and improve their
47 efficiency. The thermophysical properties (contact angle, surface tension and rheology) and
48 tribological properties (friction and wear) of potential PAO8 transmission nanofluids using CaCO_3
49 and CeF_3 nanoparticles as additives are evaluated at mass concentrations of 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and
50 0.20 wt%. Low contact angle and surface tension values are obtained, indicating good
51 wettability. When the nanoparticles are used as PAO8 additives, small reductions in surface
52 tension are achieved, but no differences in contact angle are observed. All nanolubricants and
53 base oil exhibit Newtonian behavior. Concerning the tribological behavior, reductions in the
54 friction coefficient are achieved for both types of nanoparticles, with the largest reductions
55 comparing to PAO8 base oil being 13% and 10% for nanolubricants containing 0.05 wt% CaCO_3
56 and 0.10 wt% CeF_3 nanoparticles (NPs), respectively. In terms of antiwear performance,
57 maximum reductions are obtained for the CaCO_3 nanolubricant of 28% (0.15 wt%), 41% (0.10
58 wt%) and 59% (0.15 wt%) and for the CeF_3 nanolubricant of 19% (0.20 wt%), 53% (0.10 wt%) and
59 58% (0.20 wt%) for the parameters of diameter, depth, and area of the worn track, respectively.
60 Through Raman microscopy, the tribological mechanisms of tribofilm formation, repairing, and
61 rolling can be proposed. A discontinuous tribofilm formed by the CaCO_3 and CeF_3 nanoparticles
62 reduces the contact area between the two surfaces protecting them.

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64 **Keywords:** Lubricants; EV systems; Nanoparticles; Transmissions.
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74 **1. Introduction**

75 Nowadays, electric vehicles (EVs) have become increasingly important for reducing fuel use as
76 well as pollution of air. To enhance more this positive outcome, it is crucial to improve their
77 behavior. One possible way is to enhance the tribological performance of the mechanical
78 elements and of the lubricants of the transmission power system. In many EVs, the electric
79 motor and transmission are in the same cover, in which case the electric transmission fluids
80 (ETF) must a) have a low viscosity; b) have capability to do not allow copper corrosion and also
81 be compatible with polymers, and c) exhibit suitable electrical properties [1-4]. Low viscosity
82 lubricants are used owing to the high operating speeds and torque of mechanical components
83 in EVs. Viscous drag as well as viscous heating reduce and heat transfer improves when the oil
84 viscosity is reduced [5,6]. Nevertheless, if the viscosity of the lubricant decreases, the change
85 from full film to boundary lubrication could occur, probably leading to critical surface contact
86 and cause significant wear. Therefore, advanced lubricants with good anti-wear and antifriction
87 properties are required. In this vein, an efficacious method to decrease friction and wear is using
88 nanomaterials as lubricant additives [7-12]; achieving decreases in losses of energy, wear as well
89 as pollutant emissions. There are numerous reasons for using nanoparticles (NPs) as lubricant
90 additives but most important is that because of their small size, NPs can enter in the contact
91 area, resulting in positive lubrication effects [13]. In addition, NPs as lubricant additives can act
92 through different lubrication mechanisms: rolling effect and tribo-film formation owing to direct
93 effect of the nanoparticle on the surface and mending and polishing effects due to surface
94 enhancement [14]. Moreover, the suitable nanoparticles used as additives should be less
95 chemically reactive than traditional additives, as their films are formed mechanically, so they
96 will be more durable and less reactive with other additives [15]. Another advantage of using NPs
97 as lubricant additives is their low volatility, which avoids losses at high temperature conditions
98 [15].

99 Another important quality of transmission fluids is their ability to spread on a metal surface, and
100 their wettability. Wettability is usually characterized through property measurements such as
101 contact angle or surface tension, being relevant to study its dependence on temperature. This
102 type of studies can be found for different fluids such as ionic liquids [16] or lubricants [17].
103 Currently, there are hardly any studies on the effect of the nanoadditives on the wettability
104 properties (contact angle and surface tension) of nanolubricants [18], although there are studies
105 of NPs in water [19,20]. It is therefore of particular interest to know how these properties are
106 affected by the addition of different concentrations of NPs.

107 Polyalphaolefins are widely used in various applications owing to their excellent competence as
108 base oils and their thermal and oxidative stability, which leads to enhanced performance in
109 comparison with mineral oils [15,16]. Thus, Thampi et al. [21] and Mariño et al. [22] reviewed
110 the effect of NPs and chemically modified NPs, respectively, on the tribological properties of
111 various lubricating oils, including PAOs, observing important tribological improvements with
112 different NPs. Specifically, Mariño et al. [22] found that the best tribological performance in
113 PAOs was obtained with Pd [23], TiO₂ [24] and SiO₂ [25] NPs with friction and wear reductions
114 around 40% and 90%, respectively. Furthermore, Mustafa et al. [5] reviewed some few articles
115 on low-viscosity nanolubricants, including those based on low-viscosity PAOs, finding
116 remarkable results in friction and wear. Mustafa et al. [5] and Thampi et al. [21] observed that
117 the best tribological performance was obtained by Kalin et al. [26] using MoS₂ NPs as additives
118 of PAO6, reducing the friction coefficient by more than two times, while the wear was reduced
119 by five-nine times. In this work, polyalphaolefin 8 (PAO8) was selected as the base oil because
120 its performance for electric transmissions and for its low viscosity [27]. Regarding the
121 nanoadditives, CaCO₃ and CeF₃ NPs were used as additives of the PAO8 base oil. CaCO₃ NPs are
122 environmentally friendly and verify the European Ecolabel criteria for use as lubricant additives
123 [28]. CaCO₃ NPs are generally used in the automotive industry, in construction, in plastic seals,
124 adhesives, paints, and inks. There are numerous studies on the use of calcium carbonate NPs as

125 grease additives [29-31]. However, the literature on CaCO_3 NPs as lubricating oil additives is
126 scarce [32-34]. Zhang et al. [35] studied the tribological behavior of CaCO_3 NPs as a an
127 environmentally friendly additive to PAO10 base oil, showing that CaCO_3 NPs can considerably
128 enhance the load carrying capability and the anti-wear and anti-friction-reducing properties of
129 a PAO10 base oil (88% reduction in wear volume). Kulkarni et al. [36] have investigated green
130 nanolubricants dispersing different mass concentrations of CaCO_3 NPs in jojoba oil, finding that
131 the addition of CaCO_3 NPs in the oil reveals remarkable anti-wear and extreme-pressure
132 properties, with maximum decreases in coefficient of friction and wear scar diameter of balls
133 around 35% and 40%, respectively.

134 It is worth mentioning that currently there are hardly any literature articles that use CeF_3 NPs as
135 lubricant additives [37]. Sunqing et al. [37] synthesized this type of NPs using a microemulsion
136 of water, cyclohexane and polybutene diamide, achieving NPs with an average size of 25 nm,
137 which were added to a 500SN oil-based lubricant. Tribological results showed a significant
138 reduction in the coefficient of friction (about 25%) and a slight reduction in wear. Considering
139 all the above, it is important to develop new potential low viscosity nanolubricants particularly
140 adapted to EVs and CeF_3 and CaCO_3 NPs may be excellent candidates to be used as additives for
141 further study. Thus, in this work surface tension, wettability and tribological properties of
142 potential electric transmission nanofluids based on PAO8 oil containing CaCO_3 or CeF_3 NPs as
143 additives are evaluated at mass concentrations of 0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20 wt%.

144 **2. Material and experimental methods**

145 *2.1. Materials*

146 The polyalphaolefin 8 base oil, PAO8, was provided by REPSOL. As shown in Table 1, this
147 base oil has a dynamic viscosity and density at 313.15 K of 39.47 mPa s and 0.8163 $\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$,
148 respectively, and a viscosity index of 138 [38]. The PAO8 base oil was previously characterized
149 using Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) as well as Raman spectroscopy [38].

150 **Table 1.** Main physical properties of PAO8 [38].

Nature	Density at 313.15 K g cm ⁻³	Dynamic Viscosity at 313.15 K mPa s	Viscosity index
Synthetic	0.8163	39.47	138

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152 Concerning the nanoadditives, CaCO₃ and CeF₃ NPs were delivered by US Research
 153 Nanomaterials, Inc. (Houston, TX USA). The CaCO₃ NPs have a purity of 98%, an average diameter
 154 of 50 nm, and a specific surface area of 40-80 m²/g. Furthermore, CeF₃ NPs have a size of 20 nm
 155 and a purity of 99.99%. Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM, Zeiss FESEM Ultra Plus) and
 156 Transmission Electron Microscopy (JEOL JEM-F200CF-HR) were used to know the aspect and
 157 dimension of both types of NPs. As Figs. 1 and 2 illustrate, both NPs (CaCO₃ and CeF₃) have a
 158 spherical shape, especially in the case of CaCO₃ NPs. Regarding the nanoparticle sizes, it can be
 159 observed that CaCO₃ NPs have a larger size than CeF₃ NPs. Specifically, Fig. 2 shows the size
 160 distribution of both NPs (obtained with ImageJ), observing that the average sizes for the CaCO₃
 161 and CeF₃ NPs are around 91 nm and 30 nm, respectively.

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Fig. 1 SEM images of a) CaCO₃ and b) CeF₃ nanopowders.

Fig. 2 TEM images and size nanoparticles distribution of a) CaCO_3 and b) CeF_3 nanopowders

The CaCO_3 and CeF_3 NPs were also characterized by Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) to determine the bonds associated with each NP. The FTIR spectra of the of CaCO_3 and CeF_3 NPs is shown in Fig. 3. The first one shows three prominent peaks around 710 cm^{-1} , 875 cm^{-1} and 1405 cm^{-1} corresponding respectively to a deformation in the plane, to a deformation outside in-plane and doubly degenerate in-plane strain typical of CaCO_3 [39,40]. On the other hand, the spectrum of CeF_3 NPs shows peaks detected at 736 cm^{-1} , 1494 cm^{-1} , 1637 cm^{-1} and 3384 cm^{-1} [41].

Fig. 3 FT-IR spectrum of CaCO₃ (a) and CeF₃ (b) NPs.

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Raman spectroscopy of both nanopowders was used to identify the characteristic absorption bands, Fig. 4. The CaCO₃ spectrum, Fig. 4a, shows a very strong Stokes band at 1087 cm⁻¹ and weaker ones at 160 cm⁻¹, 286 cm⁻¹, 716 cm⁻¹ and 2950 cm⁻¹, which were also found in a spectrum of the corresponding bulk material, CaCO₃ [42]. On the other hand, Fig. 4b shows the Raman spectrum of the CeF₃ NPs. In this spectrum there are two pronounced bands at 309 cm⁻¹ and 566 cm⁻¹ and other less intense bands at 993 cm⁻¹ and 1094 cm⁻¹, which match with the spectrum of the corresponding bulk material, CeF₃ [41].

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Fig. 4 Raman spectrum of CaCO_3 (a) and CeF_3 (b) NPs.

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189 CaCO_3 and CeF_3 NPs were also characterized by X-Ray diffraction to determine the crystalline
 190 form of both NPs. For this aim, a Bruker D8 Advance with Cu-K α radiation ($\lambda=1.5418$ nm) was
 191 used at room temperature. The XRD patterns were carried out between $2\theta=3-80^\circ$. The Debye-
 192 Scherrer's formula was applied to calculate the crystallite size of the nanoparticles based on the
 193 following equation [43]:

194

$$D_p = K \lambda / (B \cos \theta) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

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where D_p , K , λ , B , and θ are the average crystallite size, the Scherrer constant, the entire width
 196 at the half summit of the diffraction peak, and the Bragg angle of the peak. Fig. 5 shows the XRD

197 pattern of the CaCO_3 and CeF_3 NPs. In the CaCO_3 XRD pattern, Fig. 5a, peaks are found at
198 $2\theta=23.1^\circ, 29.41^\circ, 35.98^\circ, 39.42^\circ, 43.16^\circ, 47.52^\circ$ and 48.52° , corresponding to (012), (104), (110),
199 (113), (202), (018) and (016) crystal planes [44]. The experimental XRD pattern agrees with the
200 ICSD Card No: 98-004-0107 (Calcite) [44]. The crystallite size of CaCO_3 NPs determined from the
201 above peaks using the Eq. 1 is 96.68 nm.

202 Regarding the XRD pattern of CeF_3 NPs (Fig 5.b), peaks are found at $2\theta= 24.38^\circ, 24.93^\circ,$
203 $27.81^\circ, 43.93^\circ, 45.10^\circ, 50.92^\circ, 52.80^\circ$ and 64.80° . The experimental XRD pattern is in accordance
204 with the ICSD Card No: 98-006-4720 (Fluocerite) [45]. The crystallite size of CeF_3 NPs calculated
205 from these peaks using the Eq. 1 is 25.01 nm.

206
207 **Fig. 5** XRD pattern of CaCO_3 (a) and CeF_3 (b) NPs.

208 209 *2.2. Preparation of nanolubricants*

210 Nanolubricants were made according to the conventional two-step procedure [22].
211 Firstly, dry nanopowders (CaCO_3 or CeF_3 NPs) were mixed with PAO8 base oil, determining the
212 mass concentrations through a Sartorius MC 210P balance. For this purpose, the base oil was
213 weighed and then the amount of nanopowder required to achieve the desired mass

214 concentrations was also weighed. Secondly, the homogenization of nanodispersions was carried
215 out first with a mechanical stirrer (Fisherbrand Vortex) for 2 minutes and finally with an
216 ultrasonic bath (Fisherbrand FB11203 from Fisher Scientific, USA) for 4 h. It should be noted that
217 the preparation process the nanolubricants (formulation and homogenization) is relatively short
218 (around 6 hours. To find out the optimum mass concentration with the highest tribological
219 behavior, eight nanodispersions of PAO8 were prepared with the following additives: + 0.05 wt%
220 CaCO₃, + 0.10 wt% CaCO₃, + 0.15 wt% CaCO₃, + 0.20 wt% CaCO₃, + 0.05 wt% CeF₃, + 0.10 wt%
221 CeF₃, + 0.15 wt% CeF₃ and + 0.20 wt% CeF₃.

222 *2.3. Stability of nanolubricants*

223 To control the stability of the NPs within the oil, a simple setup is used, where the
224 samples of nanolubricants are placed with good lighting on a background of the opposite color
225 to that of the sample for better visualization. The process consists in that once the
226 nanodispersion is prepared and homogenized, it is not manipulated, and a series of photographs
227 are taken periodically at room temperature, to detect when the NPs are deposited. In this case,
228 a black background is used, and photographs were taken approximately every 24 hours.
229 Furthermore, to analyze stability more quantitative, the evolution of the refractive index over
230 time was measured by means of a refractometer (Mettler Toledo RA-510M).

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232 *2.4. Surface tension, contact angle and rheology.*

233 To carry out the surface tension measurements, a Lauda TVT 2 Drop Volume
234 Tensiometer was used, which allows measuring the surface tension through the volume of the
235 falling drop following Tate's law [46]. The fluid sample is introduced into a syringe of 2.5 ml
236 volume, being expelled from it through a needle of 1.370 mm inner radius. The temperature of
237 the lubricant sample in the syringe is controlled with a thermal bath to maintain it at 298.15 or
238 313.15 K. The uncertainty in the measured temperature was $u(T)/K=0.03$. For each surface

239 tension experiment, 30 to 40 drops are used to obtain a mean volume value with good
240 reproducibility. The uncertainty in surface tension measurements depends on the nanolubricant
241 ranging between 0.05-0.2 mN m⁻¹.

242 A Phoenix MT-A analyzer was utilized to achieve the contact angle of all the lubricants
243 on AISI 420 stainless steel plates. For the calibration of the equipment camera, a glass plate
244 supplied by the manufacturer is used, which contains reference graduation marks for different
245 contact angles. The lubricant is introduced into a syringe which, with the help of the equipment's
246 motor, makes a drop of lubricant fall on the steel plate previously cleaned with acetone. It
247 should be noted that this plate is placed on a surface that is thermostated with a bath to keep
248 the desired temperature during the analysis time. The uncertainty in the measured temperature
249 was $u(T)/K=0.5$. The obtained result is the evolution of the contact angle over time, specifically
250 its value every second for 1 minute (a series of 60 values). Several series of measurements are
251 carried out for each oil, ensuring the correct repeatability of the contact angles, taking the
252 average of all the values. The estimated uncertainty in the contact angle measurements is 2%.

253 The rheological behavior of the PAO8 base oil and its nanolubricants containing CaCO₃
254 and CeF₃ NPs was investigated with an Anton Paar MCR 101 rheometer (Graz, Austria) at 293.15,
255 333.15, and 363.15 K. The rheometer is equipped with a cone-plate geometry with a cone
256 diameter of 50 mm and a cone angle of 1°. The cone went down to an imposed gap of 0.102 mm
257 from the plate and covered the whole sample for all tests. Furthermore, the temperature is
258 controlled by means a Peltier P-PTD 200 (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria), set at the lower plate, with
259 a diameter of 56 mm. Further details of this apparatus can be found in a previous article [47].
260 Flow curves of tested lubricants were recorded in the shear rate range from 10 to 1000 s⁻¹. The
261 expanded uncertainty of viscosity measurement is estimated to be better than 5% (k=2) [47]. It
262 should be noted that an amount of 0.59 mL of sample was considered for the analysis and was
263 placed on the Peltier plate.

264 2.5. Tests of friction and wear examination

265 Ball-on-three pins friction tests with PAO8 base oil and with the eight CaCO_3 and CeF_3
266 nanolubricants were performed through a Peltier heated T-PTD200 tribology unit in an Anton
267 Paar MCR 302 rheometer (Graz, Austria). The ball is placed in a vertical tube that is powered by
268 the motor of the rheometer, while the pins, situated at the base of the holder, are touching the
269 ball at an angle of 45° with the tube. During the friction tests, the ball that supports a vertical
270 axial force applied by the rheometer, turns on the pins. This force (20 N) gives rise to three
271 identical normal forces (9.43 N) that action perpendicularly on the surfaces of the three pins. In
272 each pin, the maximum Hertzian pressure corresponds to 1.1 GPa [48]. Pins with 6 mm radius
273 and 6 mm height, and balls with 12.7 mm diameter were utilized, being both components of
274 100Cr6 hardened steel (hardness Rockwell C between 66-62). The friction tests were performed
275 at rotational speed of 213 rpm (ball surface velocity being 0.1 m s^{-1}), for 3400 s for a 393.15 K
276 temperature. Approximately 1 mL of lubricant was utilized in each test in order to cover the
277 contact surface. More information on this tribological apparatus can be found in earlier articles
278 [49,50]. The temperature was selected since for great operation of EV motors, a high-power
279 density is necessary and so the heat generation in the coil improves [30]. Nonetheless, to avoid
280 demagnetization, the temperature must be below 150°C . More information on these issues was
281 reported by Rodriguez et al. [4].

282 When the friction tests for each lubricant were completed (3 repeats for each one), the
283 wear was estimated in pins, to investigate which nanolubricant offers the best anti-wear
284 performance. Pins were cleaned with a hexane stream and dried with hot air before the wear
285 analysis. A 3D profilometer (Sensofar, S-Neox) was used to measure various worn track
286 parameters: wear scar diameter (WSD), wear track depth (WTD), worn area and roughness. It
287 should be noted that the worn area was determined using the section profile by subtracting
288 from the worn area the sum of areas of the profiles for the material displaced on both sides of

289 the worn track. All the parameters were determined in all the pins tested with all the lubricant
290 samples to obtain appropriate mean values. Moreover, a confocal Raman microscope (WITec
291 alpha300R+) was used to obtain information of the chemical organization in the worn scar and
292 to gain insight into the tribological mechanisms that may happen.

293 3. Results and discussion

294 3.1. Stability results

295 The photos corresponding to the visual stability control of the nanodispersions are
296 shown in Fig. 6. Both NPs are stable in the PAO8 base oil for at least 48 hours, which is a sufficient
297 stability time to carry out the tribological and thermophysical tests. It should be noted that Fig.
298 6 also shows that the stability decreases for both NPs when the mass concentration increases.

299

300

Fig. 6 Stability control performed on the different nanolubricants of CaCO₃ and CeF₃.

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302 The other method used to analyze the stability of the formulated nanolubricants against
 303 sedimentation is refractometry. Fig. 7 shows the evolution of the refractive index for the CaCO_3
 304 and CeF_3 nanolubricants, both with an NP concentration of 0.05 wt%. It can be clearly observed
 305 that for the 0.05 wt% CeF_3 nanolubricant after the first ten hours NPs are full sedimented,
 306 whereas in the case of the 0.05 wt% CaCO_3 nanolubricant the sedimentation is quite gradual.
 307 More precisely, for the first nanolubricant the refractive index increased 0.28% after 10 hours
 308 and for the CaCO_3 nanolubricant it increased 0.19%. It should be noted that for low viscosity oils
 309 is more difficult to find good stabilities than for viscous oils, since the nanoparticles have less
 310 resistance to falling in oil.

311

312 **Fig. 7** Refractive index evolution for 0.05 wt% CaCO_3 and CeF_3 nanolubricants

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314 **3.2. Surface tension, contact angle and rheology results.**

315 Fig. 8 and Table 2 show the values of surface tension, γ , obtained for the nanolubricants
 316 with the four mass concentrations CaCO_3 or CeF_3 NPs and the PAO8 base oil at temperatures of
 317 298.15 K and 313.15 K. It can be observed that the surface tensions of the nanodispersions are
 318 slightly lower than those of PAO8 at both temperatures. In particular, for the samples containing
 319 CeF_3 NPs the variation is almost negligible. For the case of 0.15 wt% decreases of 0.16% for
 320 $T=298.15$ K and 0.26% for $T=313.15$ K were found. On the other hand, for the nanolubricants

321 containing CaCO₃ NPs, the difference is greater, showing a minimum at 0.10 wt% with reductions
 322 of 0.64% for T=298.15 K and 0.67% for T=313.15 K. Currently, there are hardly any studies related
 323 to wettability properties (contact angle and surface tension) when nanoparticles are added to
 324 lubricants [18], although there are several studies of nanoparticles in water [19,20]. Therefore,
 325 it is critical to study how these properties are affected by the addition of different
 326 concentrations of nanoparticles.

327

328 **Fig. 8** Surface tension obtained for the base oil and its nanolubricants containing CaCO₃ or CeF₃
 329 NPs at different mass fractions, wt%, at 298.15 and 313.15 K.

330 **Table 2.**

331 Surface tension, γ , and its uncertainties, σ , of the formulated nanolubricants and the PAO8 base
 332 oil.

	298.15 K		313.15 K	
	$\gamma / \text{mN m}^{-1}$	$\sigma / \text{mN m}^{-1}$	$\gamma / \text{mN m}^{-1}$	$\sigma / \text{mN m}^{-1}$
PAO8 Base	29.61	0.07	28.33	0.07
+0.05 wt% CaCO ₃	29.51	0.10	28.24	0.08
+0.10 wt% CaCO ₃	29.42	0.09	28.14	0.09
+0.15 wt% CaCO ₃	29.53	0.17	28.17	0.10
+0.20 wt% CaCO ₃	29.57	0.07	28.27	0.06
+0.05 wt% CeF ₃	29.58	0.09	28.27	0.08
+0.10 wt% CeF ₃	29.56	0.04	28.28	0.06
+0.15 wt% CeF ₃	29.56	0.12	28.26	0.07
+0.20 wt% CeF ₃	29.57	0.05	28.28	0.04

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334 Regarding the contact angle, Fig. 9 shows the measurements of the nanolubricants with
 335 CaCO₃ and CeF₃ NPs and of the base PAO8 without additives. No clear trend is observed in in any
 336 of the cases that could indicate a significant change in the angle values of contact by the addition
 337 of NPs. It is worth mentioning that the differences are within of the uncertainty of the

338 measurements. Furthermore, it is also observed that when the temperature is increased, the
 339 values of contact angle drops. Thus, at working temperature of the EV transmissions (around
 340 393 K), the contact angle will be lower implying a superior wettability and the creation of a tribo-
 341 film that may prevent direct surface contact [51]. However, the effects of nanoadditives on
 342 wetting have not yet been explained and need to be better understood.

343 Marques et al. [17] previously studied the surface tension and contact angle of four PAO
 344 base oils (PAO6, PAO20, PAO32 and PAO40) at 293.15 K to 323.15 K, finding the same trends for
 345 viscosities, surface tensions and contact angles of PAOs. Kalin et al. [52,53] also investigated the
 346 wetting properties between some engineering surfaces (steel and several types of DLC coatings)
 347 and PAO9. These authors obtained a steady-state contact angle of 11.3° for PAO9 on the surface
 348 of steel AISI 52100 at room temperature. In the current work, a lower contact angle value has
 349 been obtained for PAO8 at room temperature (298 K), around 8°. So, the higher the molecular
 350 mass (or the viscosity grade) of the PAOs, the greater the contact angle. This result is in line with
 351 that reported by Marques et al. [17].

354 **Fig. 9** Contact angle measurements obtained for the base oil and CaCO₃ and CeF₃ nanolubricants
 355 at 298 and 313 K.

356 Concerning the rheological tests, the flow curves for the PAO8 base lubricant as well as
 357 for both types of nanolubricants (Fig. 10) at the studied mass fractions (0.05, 0.10, 0.15 and 0.20
 358 wt%) and temperatures show linear dependence of the shear stress (τ) and shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}$), the
 359 shear viscosity being the slope of such relationship. Thus, the base oil and the nanolubricants
 360 exhibit Newtonian behavior. Consequently, there is no influence of the shear rate on the
 361 viscosity for each lubricant, i.e., it is possible to determine a single viscosity value at each studied
 362 temperature without considering the flow conditions. As can be seen in the Fig. 10, there is a
 363 slight increment of the viscosity with the mass fraction, which can be considered negligible
 364 considering the studied range of the nanoparticle concentrations. As expected, temperature has
 365 a strong effect on viscosity, decreasing by up to an order of magnitude between 293.15 and
 366 363.15 K.

367
 368 **Fig. 10** Flow curves of $\text{CaCO}_3/\text{PAO8}$ (a-b) and $\text{CeF}_3/\text{PAO8}$ (c-d) nanolubricants: viscosity (a,c) and
 369 shear stress (b,d) as function of the shear rate at temperatures of 293.15 K (0 wt% ■, 0.05 wt% ●,
 370 0.10 wt% ▲, 0.15 wt% ▼, 0.20 wt% ◆), 333.15 K (0 wt% ◀, 0.05 wt% ▶, 0.10 wt% ◐, 0.15
 371 wt% ★, 0.20 wt% ◑), and 363.15 K (0 wt% +, 0.05 wt% ×, 0.10 wt% *, 0.15 wt% -, 0.20 wt% |).
 372

373 3.3. Friction and wear results.

374 Friction tests were carried out in the tribometer for the nanolubricants of PAO8 with 0.05 wt%,
375 0.10 wt%, 0.15 wt% or 0.20 wt% in CaCO_3 or CeF_3 NPs. Mean values of the coefficient of friction,
376 μ , were obtained (Fig. 11 and Table 3) for each of the studied lubricants. The μ value for the
377 PAO8 base oil has been previously measured [38], for the same operating conditions. As it can
378 be observed in Fig. 11 and in table 2, the addition of NPs as base oil additives leads to a reduction
379 in the friction coefficient with respect to the oil without additives, reaching decreases of 13%
380 for the optimal concentration of CaCO_3 NPs (0.05 wt %) and 10% for that of CeF_3 NPs (0.10 wt
381 %). It is evidently seen that for both types of nanolubricants the NP concentration influences the
382 antifriction behavior. Thus, at concentrations higher than the optimum for both NPs, the stability
383 of nanolubricants is poorer and may cause problems of nanoparticle agglomeration at the
384 contact area, because if the nanoparticle concentration is too high, nanoparticle deposition may
385 create new asperities and thus increase the friction [28].

386

387 **Fig. 11** Comparison between mean friction coefficients (μ) found with PAO8 base oil [38] as well
388 as its nanolubricants containing CaCO_3 or CeF_3 NPs at 393.15 K.

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394 **Table 3.**

395 Average friction coefficient, μ , average wear track width, WTW, average wear track depth, WTD
 396 and average worn areas with their standard deviations, σ , for the tested PAO8 lubricants at
 397 393.15 K.

Lubricant	μ	σ	WTW/ μm	$\sigma/\mu\text{m}$	WTD/ μm	$\sigma/\mu\text{m}$	Area/ μm^2	$\sigma/10\mu\text{m}^2$
PAO8 [38]	0.139	0.002	392	14	2.35	0.17	605	52
+ 0.05 wt% CaCO ₃	0.121	0.012	361	20	1.86	0.22	454	82
+ 0.10 wt% CaCO ₃	0.123	0.003	331	36	1.38	0.21	294	54
+ 0.15 wt% CaCO ₃	0.124	0.006	283	31	1.52	0.02	248	57
+ 0.20 wt% CaCO ₃	0.139	0.006	347	31	1.53	0.33	358	94
+ 0.05 wt% CeF ₃	0.128	0.003	381	46	2.05	0.41	589	62
+ 0.10 wt% CeF ₃	0.125	0.005	319	21	1.11	0.47	264	51
+ 0.15 wt% CeF ₃	0.131	0.005	356	13	1.91	0.18	472	50
+ 0.20 wt% CeF ₃	0.132	0.003	316	14	1.15	0.15	252	36

398

399 Concerning the wear produced during friction tests, the profile measurements show
 400 notable wear improvements in tested pins lubricated with nanolubricants with respect to those
 401 lubricated with PAO8 without additives (Fig. 12 and Table 3). Specifically, for nanolubricants
 402 containing CaCO₃ NPs, improvements of 28% in WSD (0.15 wt %), 41% in WTD (0.10 wt%) and
 403 59% in the area of the wear track (0.15 wt%) are achieved; while that for lubricants PAO8 + CeF₃
 404 NPs, improvements of 19% in WSD (0.20 wt %), 53% in WTD (0.10 wt%) and 58% for the area of
 405 the worn tread (0.20 wt%) are obtained. Fig. 13 shows the 3D profile and its vertical section
 406 obtained for the PAO8 base oil [38], its optimal nanolubricants with CaCO₃ NPs (0.15 wt%) or
 407 with CeF₃ NPs (0.20 wt%). Excellent wear reduction can be observed for both nanolubricants.
 408 Thus, it can be concluded that both NPs have good anti-wear ability.

409

410 Moreover, the roughness (Ra) of worn tracks of pins was examined to get more
 411 information about the anti-wear properties of CaCO₃ and CeF₃ NPs. Worn pins lubricated with
 412 both types of nanolubricants are less rough than those lubricated with PAO8 without additives
 413 (Table 4).

414 **Table 4**
 415 Mean roughness parameter Ra and its uncertainties, σ , in worn pins tested by PAO8 lubricants
 416 (Gaussian filter: 0.08 mm cut-off).
 417

Lubricant	Ra/nm	σ
PAO8 [38]	18.8	1.7
+ 0.05 wt% CaCO ₃	18.7	1.8
+ 0.10 wt% CaCO ₃	17.4	1.3
+ 0.15 wt% CaCO ₃	16.8	1.4
+ 0.20 wt% CaCO ₃	18.3	1.2
+ 0.05 wt% CeF ₃	18.7	1.3
+ 0.10 wt% CeF ₃	17.9	1.6
+ 0.15 wt% CeF ₃	17.8	1.4
+ 0.20 wt% CeF ₃	16.9	1.3

418

419 Specifically, an Ra value of 18.8 nm was observed for the worn track lubricated with
 420 PAO8, whereas the smallest Ra values (16.8 and 16.9 nm) were obtained for the surface
 421 correlated with the 0.15 wt% CaCO₃ and 0.20 wt% CeF₃ nanolubricants, resulting in a roughness
 422 reduction of about 10%. These results suggest that both nanopowders improve the surface
 423 contact area compared to the base oil, which may be due to a surface repair mechanism.

424

425 **Fig. 12** Mean a) wear scar diameters and b) worn areas achieved with PAO8 base oil and with
 426 the formulated nanolubricants.

427

428

429 **Fig. 13** 3D Surface topography of worn surfaces and cross section profiles of worn surfaces
 430 lubricated with PAO8 base oil and the optimum CaCO₃ and CeF₃ nanolubricants.

431

432 Finally, to obtain information on the distribution of NPs in worn tracks to detect the
 433 function that NPs play in reducing wear, after friction tests, Raman mappings of the worn
 434 surfaces were recorded with a confocal Raman microscope (532 nm). Previously, the Raman
 435 spectra were obtained for all the components of the nanolubricants: PAO8 base oil [38] as well
 436 as CeF₃ and CaCO₃ NPs (Fig. 4), to recognize the components in the mapping. Therefore,
 437 mappings of the worn tracks lubricated with the nanolubricants with the best anti-wear
 438 behavior, PAO8 + 0.20 wt% CeF₃ NPs, and PAO8 + 0.15 wt% CaCO₃ NPs were carried out. Fig. 14a
 439 shows the relevant areas in red and blue, in which the spectrum coincides with that obtained
 440 for CeF₃ NPs or PAO8, respectively. This information suggests that tribofilm formation (mainly
 441 due to PAO8) and repairing (for CeF₃ NPs) mechanisms occurred on the worn surface in friction
 442 tests. Regarding the Raman mapping of the track lubricated with the nanolubricant with CaCO₃
 443 NPs (Fig. 14b), the spectrum obtained in the red areas coincide with that of the CaCO₃ NPs and
 444 that obtained in the blue zones with that of PAO8. As in the case of CeF₃ NPs, the mechanism of

445 lubricant tribofilm formation (due to PAO8) and repairing (due to CaCO_3 NPs) can also be
446 observed. Therefore, considering these Raman mappings and the previous roughness results
447 two possible mechanisms of wear for both cases can be found: tribofilm formation due to oil,
448 large areas are observed in the direction of sliding, and nanoparticle repairing mechanism,
449 where NPs can be embedded in defects or deformations of the metal surface, thus having a
450 surface repair function. Due to the repairing mechanism, nanoparticles can fill the grooves and
451 scars of the rubbing surface developing in improved surface finish [54,55].

452 It should be noted that in both Fig. 14a and b, severe abrasion wear is observed in the
453 worn tracks. Usually, abrasive wear occurs when a solid object is loaded against particles of a
454 material that have equal or bigger hardness. In this case, the tribological contact is formed by a
455 two-body, where hard asperities or rigidly held grits pass over the surface like a cutting tool [56].

456

457 **Fig. 14.** Mapping Raman of worn surface tested with a) 0.20 wt% CeF_3 nanolubricant and b)
458 0.20 wt% CaCO_3 nanolubricant.

459 **4. Conclusions**

460 In this research the following results were found:

461 -Nanolubricants based on PAO8 base oil showed stabilities higher than 48h.

462 -Small decreases for nanolubricants in surface tension were obtained with reductions of 0.16%

463 (T=298.15 K) and 0.26% (T=313.15 K) for 0.15 wt% of CeF₃ and 0.64% (T=298.15 K) and 0.67%

464 (T=313.15 K) for 0.10 wt% of CaCO₃.

465 -In rheological tests, all nanolubricants and base oil exhibit Newtonian behavior.

466 -Friction coefficients for all the nanolubricants are shorter than for the PAO8 base oil: maximum
467 reductions of 13% for CaCO₃ NPs (0.05 wt %) and 10 % for CeF₃ NPs (0.10 wt %).

468 -For all the nanolubricants the wear in pins is lower for the PAO8: maximum improvements of
469 28% in WSD (0.15 wt% CaCO₃ NPs) and 19% in WSD (0.20 wt% CeF₃ NPs) are found.

470 -Through Raman, the repairing surface, tribofilm formation and ball bearing mechanisms owing
471 to the nanopowders were suggested.

472

473 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

474 **José M. Liñeira del Río:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology, Writing - original draft,

475 Writing - review & editing. **A. Alba:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology. **M. J. G.**

476 **Guimarey:** Conceptualization, Investigation, Methodology. **Jose I. Prado:** Conceptualization,

477 Investigation, Methodology. **Alfredo Amigo:** Formal analysis, supervision, validation, Writing -

478 review & editing **Josefa Fernández:** Supervision, Validation, Project administration, Funding

479 acquisition, Writing - review & editing.

480 **Declaration of competing interest**

481 None.

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